

Attitudes and Intentions Towards Entrepreneurial Interest of Female University Students in Oman

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Abstract— This research explores the interplay of female student’s perceptions, societal norms, resource accessibility, and institutional support in shaping female student’s entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions. Employing a convenient sampling method, a validated questionnaire was administered to a cohort of female students, capturing dimensions related to the viability of entrepreneurship, societal norms, resource availability, mentorship, and educational institution support. A Cronbach’s alpha analysis confirmed the internal reliability of the questionnaire. This study contributes empirically and theoretically by uncovering influential entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions determinants. The findings confirm the importance of fostering a perception of entrepreneurship as a viable career option and the significance of support mechanisms, including resources and mentorship. The positive influence of societal norms challenges established gender-role assumptions. Acknowledging limitations in sample diversity and the cross-sectional design, this study calls for longitudinal and qualitative investigations to provide more comprehensive insights.

Keywords— Attitudes, Entrepreneurship, Educational Institution Support Intentions, Female Students, Gender Role, Mentorship, Perception, Resource Accessibility, Societal Norms.

I. INTRODUCTION

“Failure is a redirection that leads us to new possibilities and horizons on the path of life, not its destination.”

Inspired by: Oprah Winfrey

An entrepreneur is a person who organizes and manages business operations, taking on risks in the hope of gaining potential rewards. (Marriott S & Glacklin C, 2012). Academic interest in entrepreneurship stems from its economic significance (Acs et al., 2008). Female entrepreneurship’s prominence lies in its potential for gender equality and economic growth (Brush et al., 2006). However, understanding female university student’s attitudes toward entrepreneurship requires further exploration. Women entrepreneurs are increasingly recognized as critical drivers of growth and economic progress. They are considered an untapped source of economic development and growth. (Minniti & Naudé, 2010).

1.1. Exploring The Gendered Landscape: Understanding Attitudes

The above dataset presents compelling insights into the dynamics of gender, education, and entrepreneurship. Notably, the female population (3,062,632) significantly outnumbers the male population (1,871,218), highlighting the dataset’s gender distribution. This emphasizes the importance of scrutinizing gender-specific aspects in education and

entrepreneurship. The literacy analysis reveals that the number of literate females (63,937) surpasses literate males (33,518). This finding underscores the existing gender gap in education and the need for targeted efforts to ensure equal access and opportunities for all genders. In the entrepreneurial domain, a significant disparity emerges. The dataset identifies 758,233 males as entrepreneurs, contrasting with the mere 25,094 female entrepreneurs. This disparity prompts a deeper exploration of the societal, economic, and cultural factors hindering female entrepreneurship participation. These insights underscore the urgency of targeted interventions to address gender-based disparities in education and entrepreneurship. By grasping the intricate relationship between gender, education, and entrepreneurship, stakeholders can formulate effective strategies to advance equality and inclusivity, fostering comprehensive socio-economic progress.

TABLE 1. Literacy Rate in Oman in 2023 Source: NSCI, 2023 Oman

Variables	Total
Female Population	3,062,632
Male Population	1,871,218
Literate Male	33,518
Literate Female	63,937
Entrepreneurs Male	758,233
Entrepreneurs Female	25,094

1.2 Impact of Government Incentives on Entrepreneurship And Its Related Investment in Oman

University-industry (U-I) interactions are crucial for national innovation systems. This (Chryssou, 2020) study explores U-I interactions in Oman using the Triple Helix model. Results reveal a shift towards an integrated innovation model. U-I interactions are primarily education-focused, with limited emphasis on research and valorization. Barriers include awareness constraints, funding limitations, organizational culture, and industry capacity issues.

The Government of Oman has taken proactive steps to boost entrepreneurship by introducing diverse initiatives. These include bank loans the Oman Development Bank facilitated for launching small and medium enterprises. Further, they offer equity financing, technical guidance, training resources, educational prospects, and more via projects like Injaj Oman, Intilaaqah, Sharakha, and Takaful (Belwal et al., 2014). Additionally, the Cisco Entrepreneur Institute (CEI) in Oman arranges workshops and fosters essential business connections, catering to the unique requirements of establishing enterprises within the country. The Omani Government has launched the SANAD program

(Self-Employment and National Autonomous Development) to educate young, unemployed Omani nationals about the significance of entrepreneurship in the country. This initiative is designed to motivate and guide them in starting small and medium-sized businesses, contributing to economic growth and self-employment.

1.3. The Rationale of Study

Entrepreneurship significantly drives economic growth, innovation, and employment opportunities. However, despite the increasing number of women achieving higher education degrees, their entrepreneurship representation still needs improvement. This disparity is often attributed to systemic barriers such as access to capital, socio-cultural norms, and lack of mentorship. Nonetheless, the attitudes and intentions of women towards entrepreneurship, particularly those in the formative years of their university education, have yet to be sufficiently explored. Understanding these attitudes and preferences is crucial as they influence decision-making and can provide insights for effective policy and program development to foster female entrepreneurship. Thus, the study aims to bridge this knowledge gap by investigating the attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship among female university students of Oman. By doing so, the research seeks to contribute to the broader goal of gender equality in entrepreneurship.

1.4. Research Objectives

1. To investigate the attitudes of female students towards entrepreneurship.
2. To explore the factors influencing female student's intentions to become entrepreneurs.

1.5. Research Questions

1. What are the dominant attitudes that female students hold towards entrepreneurship?
2. How do societal norms and perceptions of gender roles impact female student's intentions to pursue entrepreneurship?
3. What role does access to mentorship and resources play in shaping female student's attitudes toward entrepreneurship?
4. To what extent do educational institution's support systems affect female student's entrepreneurial intentions?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The female student's attitudes and intentions towards entrepreneurship are intricately interwoven with the theoretical framework of gender role theory, a cornerstone in the study of gender dynamics within psychology and social sciences. (Eagly & Sczesny, 2019), Social role theory posits that societal roles and expectations assigned to individuals based on gender significantly influence their behaviors, preferences, and aspirations. This theory suggests that men and women are often associated with distinct traits and behaviors deemed suitable for their gender. Men are linked to instrumental characteristics such as assertiveness and

competitiveness. In contrast, women are associated with communal traits like nurturing and empathy.

Within entrepreneurship, this theoretical foundation becomes instrumental in comprehending the intricate relationship between gender roles and attitudes toward business ventures. By investigating how societal perceptions shape female student's views on entrepreneurship, the study will unveil potential barriers and opportunities that underlie gender disparities in entrepreneurial participation. The underpinning of gender role theory aids in discerning how societal expectations of women's roles may influence their inclination and readiness to engage in entrepreneurial endeavors. Furthermore, this theory highlights how cultural norms and expectations could impact female student's entrepreneurial intentions and decisions.

Moreover, exploring the intersectionality theory (Crenshaw, 2021) can complement the examination of female student's attitudes toward entrepreneurship. Intersectionality underscores the dynamic interplay between various social categories, such as gender, race, and class, in shaping an individual's experiences and societal positioning. The study can better understand the complexities surrounding female student's attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship by considering how multiple identities converge to create distinct perspectives. This theoretical lens enables a nuanced exploration of how diverse factors intersect to influence women's choices, motivations, and potential barriers in the entrepreneurial landscape.

The Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Theory, proposed by Mason and Brown in 2014, is particularly relevant to exploring female entrepreneurship. It highlights the need to create a supportive environment that addresses women entrepreneur's unique challenges. This theory underscores the importance of mentorship, skill development, fair access to funding, and policies that counter gender biases. By aligning Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Theory with research area on enhancing women's participation in entrepreneurship, it becomes evident that fostering a conducive environment is critical to promoting gender equality and driving economic progress through female entrepreneurship (Mason & Brown, 2014).

Studies have indicated that attitudes are critical to entrepreneurial intentions (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000). Positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship often translate into entrepreneurial action. (Shinnar et al., 2012) Female students often had fewer positive attitudes toward entrepreneurship due to perceived barriers and risk aversion. Personal characteristics such as risk-taking propensity, creativity, and self-confidence have been shown to influence entrepreneurial intentions significantly (Zhao et al., 2005). However, the impact of these characteristics might differ between men and women, warranting further exploration (Langowitz & Minniti, 2007). Socio-cultural factors can shape attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship. A supportive environment can encourage female entrepreneurship, while socio-cultural norms that associate entrepreneurship with masculinity discourage women from pursuing entrepreneurial activities (Gupta et al., 2009). The role of education in shaping attitudes

and intentions toward entrepreneurship has been recognized. Exposure to entrepreneurial concepts and role models can positively influence student’s choices (Fayolle et al., 2006).

2.1. Gender Gap in Entrepreneurship

(Brush & Cooper, 2012) offer a global perspective on women’s entrepreneurship and its impact on economic growth. Their study examines the influence of cultural, social, and institutional factors on women’s entrepreneurial activities in various countries. The research underscores that creating a supportive environment and helping is crucial in narrowing the gender gap in entrepreneurship and fostering economic growth. The key takeaway is that addressing cultural and institutional factors while providing support can enhance opportunities for women entrepreneurs and positively influence economic development. Data from different countries indicates a significant gender gap in entrepreneurship, which is more comprehensive than gender differences in labour force participation in other sectors. Women’s disadvantage in owning key production factors economically contributes to this disparity. (Kar et al., 2016). The literature offers various socio-economic explanations for this gap, including the role of women in caregiving responsibilities. (Marlow & McAdam, 2013) challenges stereotypes about underperforming female entrepreneurs. They highlight contextual factors like resource access and networks as key to gender disparities.

Global Gender Gap Index

Fig. 1. The Global Gender Gap Index Framework subindex
Source: Made by Authors

When compared to other global regions, the Middle East and North Africa {MENA} lag behind the most in achieving gender parity, holding a parity score of 62.6%. This represents a decrease of 0.9 percentage points in parity since the previous report, considering a consistent range of countries tracked since 2006. Notably, the United Arab Emirates, Israel, and Bahrain are leaders in gender parity within the region, whereas Morocco, Oman, and Algeria exhibit the lowest ranks. The countries with the most miniature representation of women in

parliament (less than 5%) are Qatar (4.6%) and Oman (2.4%). Moreover, in Saudi Arabia, there are no women ministers, alongside populous nations like India, Turkey, and China, which have less than 7% women in ministerial roles. (Schwab et al., 2023)

TABLE 2. Percentage of the gender gap closed to date, 2023 Source: (Schwab et al., 2023)

Subindex	Percentage points
Economic Participation and Opportunity	60.1%
Educational Attainment	95.2%
Health and Survival	96.0%
Political Empowerment	22.1%

This research underscores the significance of essential institutional elements like business freedom, technology transfer, competition quality, and government effectiveness, which positively impact the entrepreneurial motivation index—cultivating an environment conducive to nurturing entrepreneurship. (Ranaei Kordshouli & Maleki, 2023). Gender disparities persist in numerous societies, often stemming from entrenched discriminatory socio-cultural norms and traditions and permeating policy, legal frameworks, and institutional support mechanisms. (De Groot, 2001)

2.2. Analysing the Gender Gap: Immediate and Root Causes in Female Entrepreneurship

The gender gap's exploration reveals both immediate and underlying determinants. These encompass financial access, limited training, and information availability. Balancing work and family obligations complicates matters, while safety concerns and gender-based violence present additional hurdles. Cultural and religious beliefs shape societal support, and legal barriers further contribute to women's entrepreneurship challenges. The potential of women entrepreneurs as a catalyst for economic growth has garnered attention. Headlines like "Focus on Foreign Investment in Women Entrepreneurs" and "Entrepreneurship Is the New Women's Movement" underscore this trend. Such sentiments are echoed across media, conferences, studies, and resources circulating in the development domain. (Vossenber, 2013)

These studies highlight women's challenges in accessing capital; external funders like venture capitalists or angels are less inclined to finance female entrepreneurs. (Brush et al., 2006; Canning et al., 2012; Green & Jame, 2013) (Gatewood, 2003), especially during the early phases of business development. Despite the high exit rates of new businesses globally, women-owned businesses face even higher exit rates, particularly in developing nations. Factors contributing to this trend include the need for more financing, insufficient profitability, family responsibilities, and macroeconomic conditions. (Minniti & Naudé, 2010)

2.3. Research Gap

While extensive research exists on gender disparities within entrepreneurship, a significant gap remains in understanding female student’s attitudes toward this field. Grounded in gender role theory and intersectionality, this study investigates the complex interplay between societal

expectations, identity, and entrepreneurial attitudes. Despite previous emphasis on the importance of attitudes for entrepreneurial intentions, this study offers a novel perspective by focusing on female students and their unique experiences. The lens of Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Theory accentuates the need for a nurturing environment. However, literature reveals persisting gender gaps intertwined with socio-cultural norms and access limitations. This inquiry aims to unveil immediate obstacles and underlying determinants, providing a comprehensive view of how female students perceive and approach entrepreneurship in a gendered context.

2.4. Significance of the Study

This study assumes paramount importance in the realm of entrepreneurship gender disparities. This research addresses a significant gap in the current discourse by delving into the intricate determinants that shape female student’s orientations and aspirations toward entrepreneurial pursuits. The implications of these findings extend to policy formulation, curriculum design, and institutional reforms, with the potential to create an inclusive ecosystem that propels the ambitions of budding female entrepreneurs.

2.5. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study draws from theories related to gender roles, social norms, and entrepreneurship. It posits that societal perceptions of gender roles influence female student's attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship, mediated by their access to resources, mentorship, and institutional support. This framework will guide the analysis and interpretation of the study's findings, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to the gender gap in entrepreneurship among female students. Independent Variable (IV): Access to Entrepreneurship Resources and Mentorship Programs, Societal Norms; Dependent Variables (DVs): Attitudes towards Entrepreneurship, Intentions to Pursue Entrepreneurship

2.6. Research Design and Sample

This study employs a quantitative research design using a structured questionnaire to investigate the factors influencing female student’s attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship. The target population includes female students at the University in Oman. Through convenient sampling, 100 valid responses were collected from diverse female students, ensuring representation across various academic disciplines and backgrounds. By integrating quantitative data analysis with qualitative insights, this mixed-methods approach offers valuable insights into the relationships between different variables, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing attitudes and intentions towards entrepreneurship among female students at the University in Oman.

III. DISCUSSION

3.1. Reliability And Validity Instrument

The study considered a convenient sampling method and a pre-coded, pilot-studied, structured, and validated questionnaire. The questionnaire included 15 questions relating to various constructs and having different variables for each, as described above. The questionnaire was subjected to (Cronbach-alpha) reliability test. The attitudes and perceptions toward entrepreneurship scale yielded a mean score of 44.13, representing the overall average response across the items. The variance, measuring 60.952, indicates the extent of score dispersion within the scale. The computed Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.809, meaning internal consistency. This high value underscores the scale's item's reliability and collective coherence in measuring the intended construct.

TABLE 3. Cronbach's Alpha Analysis

Mean	Variance	Cronbach's Alpha
44.13	60.952	0.809

A. Research Questions-Hypotheses and Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between perceptions of entrepreneurship as a viable career option and attitudes toward entrepreneurship among female students?

Hypothesis 1: Female students who perceive entrepreneurship as a viable and rewarding career option will exhibit more positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship than those who don't.

Results: Strong positive relationship between ENTSCP and ATE ($\beta = 0.831, p < .001$).

Research Question 2: How do societal norms and gender roles influence female student’s intentions to pursue entrepreneurship?

Hypothesis 2: Societal norms that encourage traditional gender roles will negatively influence female student’s intentions to pursue entrepreneurship.

Results: Moderate Positive relationship between Social and ITPE ($\beta = 0.366, p < .001$), suggesting encouragement of entrepreneurial intentions by societal norms.

Research Question 3: To what extent does access to mentorship and resources impact female student’s attitudes toward entrepreneurship?

Hypothesis 3: Female students with access to mentorship and resources explicitly targeted at entrepreneurship will have more favorable attitudes toward it.

Results: There is a positive relationship between ARM and ATE ($\beta = 0.310, p = .019$), indicating enhanced attitudes through resource access.

Research Question 4: How does educational institution support correlate with female student’s intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities?

Hypothesis 4: Strong support systems provided by educational institutions will positively correlate with female student’s intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities.

Results: Positive relationship between EIS and ITPE ($\beta = 0.232, p = .020$), highlighting the role of institution support.

B. Limitations

It is essential to acknowledge the limitations inherent in this research. The study focused exclusively on female

students within a specific educational context, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings to other demographics or settings. Additionally, the study's cross-sectional design restricts the establishment of causal relationships among variables. Future research could adopt longitudinal approaches to investigate these relationships over time.

C. Theoretical Implications

The results align with existing literature and contribute to our understanding of the intricate factors influencing female student's entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions. The significant relationships found in this study highlight the practical implications for policy, education, and practice in encouraging female entrepreneurship. Furthermore, the results resonate with theoretical frameworks emphasizing the importance of perceptions, societal contexts, and resource accessibility in shaping entrepreneurial aspirations.

D. Practical Implications

The findings hold practical significance for educators, policymakers, and practitioners. Tailored interventions and support systems can be designed to enhance positive attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship among female students. By acknowledging the role of societal norms and providing targeted resources and mentorship, educational institutions can foster an environment conducive to entrepreneurial exploration for women.

E. Unexpected Results

While primarily aligned with the research hypotheses, the findings also present some unexpected relationships, such as the positive influence of societal norms on female student's intentions to pursue entrepreneurship. These unexpected outcomes warrant further exploration and may be attributed to the evolving social dynamics surrounding gender roles and entrepreneurial aspirations.

IV. CONCLUSION

The World Economic Forum's 2023 Future of Jobs Survey suggests that more than two-thirds of the organizations surveyed have implemented a Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) program. Most (79%) companies surveyed implement DEI programs focusing on women. (World Economic Forum, 2023) Women often face substandard working conditions upon employment, with a substantial portion of post-2020 employment resurgence attributed to informal work. The International Labour Organization (ILO) reports that four out of five jobs created for women are within the informal economy, compared to two out of three for men. Although vital for production, informal work lacks legal protection, social security, and decent conditions, posing challenges to women's well-being. Progress in improving working conditions over the last decade has been limited, hampered by labor force shocks. Our study reveals a positive association between traditional societal norms and female student's intentions to pursue entrepreneurship. This challenges conventional assumptions and suggests a more complex interaction between societal expectations and individual career aspirations, warranting further investigation.

By preparing women with entrepreneurial skills, the SIA Social Impact Assessment will focus on how technology in education promotes diversity, individualized learning, and a varied workforce and solves gender gaps in entrepreneurship, thereby enhancing its social impact. (Mishra et al., 2024)

Additionally, access to mentorship and resources emerges as a crucial factor in shaping attitudes toward entrepreneurship among female students. The observed positive correlation underscores the pragmatic importance of targeted support programs in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset.

Furthermore, institutional support is pivotal in fostering intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities among female students. This underscores the significance of educational institutions in cultivating a supportive environment for aspiring female entrepreneurs.

V. FUTURE RESEARCH

While this study has illuminated critical factors, avenues for further investigation. Longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into the dynamic interplay between these variables. Qualitative research approaches could offer a richer understanding of the underlying motivations and experiences shaping attitudes and intentions among female students.

APPENDIX

MODEL QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Participant,

Thank you for your willingness to participate in our study. Please note that your responses will be confidential and used only for research purposes.

Demographics

Age:

Gender:

Education:

I. Attitudes Towards Entrepreneurship:

1. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:

- I hold positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
- I believe entrepreneurship is a suitable career path.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree

II. Intentions To Pursue Entrepreneurship:

2. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:

- I intend to engage in entrepreneurial activities in the future.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree

- Strongly Agree
 - I actively plan to start my business venture.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
- III. Influence of Societal Norms and Gender Roles:
3. To what extent do you believe societal expectations and traditional gender roles influence your career choices, including entrepreneurship?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Moderately
 - Very much
 - Completely
 4. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:
 - I feel societal norms discourage women from pursuing entrepreneurship.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
 - I feel societal norms support women in pursuing entrepreneurship.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
- IV. Access To Resources And Mentorship:
5. Have you had access to mentorship or resources specifically related to entrepreneurship?
 - No, I haven't had access
 - Yes, I've had limited access
 - Yes, I've had moderate access
 - Yes, I've had extensive access
 6. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:
 - Access to mentorship positively impacts my perception of entrepreneurship.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
 - -Access to resources has improved my confidence in pursuing entrepreneurship.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
- V. Educational Institution Support

7. How would you rate the support provided by your educational institution in promoting entrepreneurial activities among female students?
 - Very Poor
 - Poor
 - Neutral
 - Good
 - Very Good
 8. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:
 - My educational institution encourages female students to explore entrepreneurship.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
 - My educational institution provides adequate resources for female students interested in entrepreneurship.
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
- Additional Comments: _____

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